

SWIFTERS: A Multi-UAV Platform for Disaster Management

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Abstract—In this paper we present SWIFTERS, a technology platform for utilising multiple UAVs in disaster management. The platform aims to provide fast situational awareness and improve the effectiveness of disaster management operations by exploiting UAV deployment opportunities. The platform allows flying UAVs in a click-and-go fashion, scanning an area using multiple collaborating UAVs while receiving live video feed from the camera of the UAVs' to detect people, vehicles and carry out visual disaster assessment. This paper provides evidence of the reliability and scalability of the SWIFTERS platform in a real-life experiment with four UAVs.

Index Terms—Unmanned aerial vehicles, Multi-agent systems, Emergency services, Software systems.

I. INTRODUCTION

Unmanned Aerial Vehicles or simply UAVs, have shown their potential in multiple areas of our lives including tackling some of the most challenging tasks to human beings such as natural disasters [1], [2], [3]. Although the natural disasters cannot be avoided, their effects could be significantly mitigated through a comprehensive and highly efficient disaster management system. Time is the most essential factor in successful disaster management and hence disaster response must be designed and carried out swiftly based on accurate assessments of the situation.

Conventional disaster management systems typically rely on ground emergency response efforts to carry out disaster assessments. However, such approaches are resource hogging and greatly affect the disaster assessment time. Additionally, following a disaster event, access on the ground may be severely constrained; making it impossible for the first responders to effectively carry out their tasks, as indicated in Lettieri et al. [4].

UAVs have the potential to enhance and optimise all phases of disaster management including disaster assessment [5]. At the pre-disaster stage, UAVs can be used to accurately predict the outbreak and assist in disaster prevention activities with only a fraction of the resources needed by conventional operations [6]. During the disaster, UAVs can provide high-resolution, real-time views of the most inaccessible locations which can then be used to produce high-quality maps and aid rescuers in accurately assessing the situation, provide relief and conduct rescue [7]. In the post-disaster stage, UAVs can be used to map the affected areas and aid in the reconstruction of the damaged infrastructure [8].

First responder units (such as police departments, fire brigades and civil protection) that have integrated UAV platforms in their operations rely merely on their manual control.

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This is achieved by either using the remote controller of the UAV or via a mobile phone application that provides generic UAV control features [7]. However, manually operating UAVs requires a sufficient number of trained pilots and accompanied personnel (visual observers, spotters, technical support) imposing a great challenge in the available human resource pool. Also, it increases the stress caused to the team members (as indicated in [9]) and the operation is more prone to errors especially when undertaking multi-UAV tasks; such as searching of an area using multiple UAVs to minimise the disaster assessment time [10].

Multi-UAV platforms enable the use of a fleet of aerial units to conduct numerous activities in parallel and handle flying patterns to maximise performance. In addition, the operator of the system maintains a global view at all times (hence improving safety), and receives live feed from the on-board sensors (e.g. cameras) for acquiring real-time situational awareness.

Currently, the available multi-UAV platforms are restricted in the type of UAVs they support and the features that they provide especially for emergency response operations. For instance, the offline use of the system (i.e., without Internet connection) is a key feature in emergency response missions that has not been looked at to date. Multi-UAV operations have also not been introduced to existing solutions and is one of the main features that our proposed system aims to address.

Hence, the main contribution of this paper is the design, development and implementation of a multi-UAV platform dedicated to assisting response units throughout the life cycle of disaster management. The platform enables real-time monitoring (using the onboard sensors), live video transmission from all connected UAVs, video analytics (object detection done in real time) and mission planning tools using state-of-the-art multi-agent algorithms, taking into account the challenges posed by the UAVs and the operational environment. The platform is designed to enable integration with modules developed in any programming language and framework. It can support any type of programmable UAV through a dedicated interface, includes a database for storing persistent data and can run completely offline from a single or more computing devices. To demonstrate the applicability of the proposed solution, a real-life experiment was carried out with accompanied results to evaluate the performance of the proposed software platform. The results presented hereafter provide evidence of the reliability and the scalability of the proposed SWIFTERS platform.

The rest of the paper is split into the following sections. Related work is included in Section II while Section III elaborates on the proposed framework and presents in-detail the system architecture and discusses some of the most important components. Section IV presents the methodology

of the experiment. In particular, it provides details on the scenario followed and the equipment used. Section V presents the performance evaluation results and provides evidence of the reliability and scalability of the proposed SWIFTERS platform. Section VI concludes with a summary of the main outcomes of this paper and directions for future work.

II. RELATED WORK

Over the last several years multiple open-source and commercial software platforms have been developed to facilitate multi-UAV applications. Such platforms are frequently referred to as Ground Control Stations (GCSs) with the most popular being the DJI FlightHub, UgCs, Mission Planner by Ardupilot and DroneSense. We briefly review each of the aforementioned platforms and in the process we underline missing features and need of a multi-UAV platform dedicated for disaster management missions.

DJI FlightHub [11], developed by DJI offers team management and flight management operations and supports direct integration with some of the most popular UAVs by DJI that provide the mobile and onboard SDKs. FlightHub provides a map view which allows the platform administrator to monitor where UAVs operate in real time as well as the main information of each operation such as the operating pilot, the UAV in use and the geo-location of the operation. Flight hub allows the platform administrator to access live video feeds of up to four UAVs as part of its Real-Time View feature. FlightHub also offers Team Management features such as specifying the Administrators, Captains and Pilots and even associating a pilot with a particular UAV. At the moment, DJI FlightHub is focused on team and fleet operations and does not offer any autonomous flying features such as instructing a UAV to visit a particular location or multiple UAVs to collaboratively search an area.

The Universal Ground Control Station (UgCs)[12] is another popular platform for handling multiple UAVs. It offers a 3D interface and supports the addition of map layers from external map providers. It supports APM and Pixhawk controllers as well as UAVs from popular manufacturers such as DJI and Mikrokopter. Additionally, UgCS supports DEM files to be imported as well as overlay of external data such as those from ADS-B transponders. It allows controlling and navigating a UAV using either the Click-and-Go mode or Joystick mode. It includes features for geo-tagging and video recording and has a telemetry player which allows the replay of all recorded flights. Moreover, UgCS allows the user to create custom no-fly zones - areas where the UAVs should not visit, while it also comes with built-in no-fly zones around all major airports. UgCS also supports multi-node installation, meaning that the system can run on a central server and allow multiple pilots to connect using the UgCS software. UgCS is available for Windows, Mac OS X and Ubuntu and is licensed under a free open source licence. However, a paid version is required for using more than two UAVs. Additionally, although the multiple operation features offered by UgCS the creation and allocation of tasks to each UAV is fully manual and no multi-UAV operation features are supported.

Mission Planner [13] is another multi-drone ground station application which was created by the ArduPilot open source project. It includes mission features such as the Click-and-Go waypoint entry and it enables choosing from a variety of maps (e.g., Google Maps [14], OpenStreetMaps [15]). MissionPlanner also allows using a joystick to operate the UAV and offers a plethora of mission commands in drop-down menus including monitoring an area. In addition, it allows the generation and download of flight logs to keep track of the UAV flights.

DroneSense [16] is promoted as a ground control station that supports any smart device and any UAV. DroneSense allows the operators to plan autonomous flights for a mission in advance. During the flight it allows the operator to watch the view of the UAVs during the entire flight and enables the mission administrator to track pilot hours, battery packs, payloads, and historical weather. After the flight, any operator of the platform can play back flights in detail including telemetry and any other captured media. Additionally, the platform allows users to create 3D models during flight and use them later to plan any routine data collection. DroneSense enables the mission operator to manage the pilots and also provides tools to support on the organisation of the policies, procedures and materials. Also DroneSense provides an interface which allows the user to create custom reports, create and enforce pilot checklists, set and automatically apply media retention policies, convey all internal policies and procedures, filling NOTAMs electronically with ease and store training materials and manuals, between others. Additionally, it offers the functionality required to record any incidents occurred during a flight and associate them with the pertinent equipment or personnel. DroneSense does not support any mission planning capabilities (such as setting waypoints for a UAV) however, it can be combined with the DroneSense Pilot [17] mobile app which includes such automated features. Similarly to the previous platforms presented in this section, no multi-UAV operations are provided to DroneSense nor DroneSense Pilot [17].

Apart from the commercial solutions presented above, initial steps in developing multi-UAVs platforms and applications have been demonstrated in research facilities over the recent past. Schmittle et al. [18] presented an open source testbed for UAV education and research. This testbed allows for multi-UAV swarm formations, however it can only be used for simulations rather than actual UAVs in real environments. Similarly, Chudoba et al. [?] presented an experimental testbed for autonomous multi-rotor applications. Wu et al. [19] recently presented a collaborative UAV framework that features algorithms for divergence avoidance, energy simulation and path planning. Although a variety of algorithms are offered, the platform lacks in providing a user-friendly interface for allocating missions to the UAVS and in receiving live-feed from the UAVs' payloads

Each of the GCSs reviewed in this section supports different types of UAVs, run on different platforms, and have different requirements and capabilities. Some of them focus more on the mission operation (flying the UAVs through the application) while others focus on the team operation and the manage-

ment of the the pilots. While they have multiple advantages, the aforementioned platforms lack in utilising autonomous features (swarm path planing algorithms), computer vision (such as detecting objects and people), or enabling mult-UAV tasking considering the UAV physical limitations including for example the battery life. Additionally, the above platforms, in their majority, lack in integration with other third-party software and typically support only UAVs manufactured by a single company. Hence the current state-of-the-art solutions do not adequately deliver on a reliable platform that purposefully utilises the potentials of UAV swarms to fulfill the needs emerging in the life cycle of disaster management. As we elaborate in the sequel, this work tries to address this gap by providing a flexible and scalable platform that focuses on autonomous features that address the real-time needs of first responders in the field.

III. SWIFTERS SYSTEM ARCHITECTURE

Fig. 1. System architecture of the SWIFTERS multi-UAV platform

SWIFTERS, the multi-UAV platform proposed in this paper enables the utilisation of multiple UAVs in disaster management operations. Using this platform, users can monitor the real-time state and position of each of the connected UAVs. Users can also instruct UAVs to visit a particular location in a click-and-go fashion, autonomously search an area while viewing live feeds from the camera views of the collaborating UAVs and enable visual disaster assessment.

A. System Architecture

The architecture of the system is presented in Figure 1. As shown in the schematic, the system consists of four main modules: a) the Graphical User Interface, b) a Ground Control Station, c) a Task-as-a-Service module, d) a UAV-as-a-Service module and e) a database module.

The Graphical User Interface is used to enable the utilization of the SWIFTERS platform in an intuitive and user friendly way. It provides the overall status of the UAV states (including their telemetry and battery levels) and enables sending commands to one or more UAVs at the same time. Additionally, and as further described below, it enables the reception of real-time video feed from the UAV cameras and the implementation

of image processing algorithms. The Ground Control Station includes important components for the functioning and the stability of the platform. The most important component is the ROS (Robotic Operating System) master which orchestrates the communication between the User interface, the ground control station and the UAVs via the ROS library [20]. A Map Server is used to enable offline maps availability, a Database manager to enable the storing of persistent data and a Video Web Streamer to receive real-time video feed from the UAVs and making it available to the interested parties. The Ground Control station also includes important modules for enabling the extend-ability of the SWIFTERS platform. The Drone Manager enables the support of UAVs of multiple manufacturers, as long as they are programmable or SDKs/APIs are provided by their manufacturers. This is achieved by the use of interfacing mobile apps that implement the UAV’s manufacturer SDK and can communicate with SWIFTERS. Thus far, the platform has been tested using DJI UAVs [21].

The Task manager enables the support of various tasks (such as instructing UAVs to go to a specific location and deliver a package, or more complex algorithms for image processing and people detection). Example tasks already implemented in the platform include the monitoring of a particular location and collaborative searching. The monitoring point task works in a click-and-go fashion, where the user can select a UAV, select some points on the map and then click the “GO” command to initiate the mission. Collaborative searching enables the utilisation of multiple UAVs to scan an area. The background algorithm, described in detail in [22] takes into account the battery of the UAVs and their estimated maximum flight time to produce paths for each of the selected UAVs in a variation of the Vehicle Routing Problem. The Task manager enables the introduction of more tasks that can extend the usability and enhance the purpose of the SWIFTERS platform.

The complete SWIFTERS platform is containerised in a Docker [23] through the 64-bit Ubuntu 18.04.02 LTS Operating System and all required libraries to ease its successful deployment.

B. User Interface

1) *Main application*: The main application platform which includes the user interface is shown in Fig. 2 It has been programmed in JAVA [24] and it consists of different components: a top menu, a base map, UAV info panels, and a quick command buttons at the bottom of the screen. The top menu includes a list of tasks for different disaster management operations such as the monitoring a point or searching an area. The Maps section allows the user to select from multiple available online and offline maps. The View section enables the user to make the different menus provided visible or invisible. In the Settings section, the user can add or remove UAVs, or modify their details. In the About section, information about the implementation of the platform and where to find help is listed. The Videos section enables receiving the video of the UAVS and includes modules for object detection, extensively discussed later in this paper. The main map shows

the location of each UAV and the current battery level of the UAV. At the centre of the interface, a map is used to reflect the location of the UAVs, keep track of their movements and their progress towards the evolution of the mission. UAV Info panels are provided to the left hand side of the screen to present important information regarding the state of the UAVs such as the current position (latitude, longitude, altitude) and vital information (including battery level, and any warning messages). At the bottom of the user interface, quick access command buttons are provided for UAV tasking including synchronised take-off and landing, pause and resume task features, cancel mission and return home commands. Alerts that notify for low battery or disconnected drones are provided to enhance the safety and usability of the system as shown in the right hand side. It is important to note that although the platform offers the ability to monitor an area collaboratively with multiple drones that no object-avoidance capability is provided at the version presented in this paper. In the current version, the user shall be aware of any static obstacles to avoid/fly above, while the avoidance of collision between the drones is handled by time/space separation. Figure 2, presents a real demo undertaken with three UAVs which have been instructed to monitor an area and we can observe the created points, as well as the path undertaken by the UAVs thus far.

2) *Live Feed and Detection module:* The real-time video received from the camera of any UAV can be obtained and processed using the Live Feed and Detection module presented in Fig. 4.

As shown, the video from the UAV is displayed in the middle and buttons are provided to zoom in or out, to turn the UAV camera gimball, to enable detections and record the video in a file. The module supports full screen mode to provide the user with a better experience.

The detection of people, vehicles and other important objects is achieved using the Tensorflow framework [25]. Tensorflow is an open source machine learning library and framework which enables the training, testing and usage of machine learning models in a plethora of tasks including object detection on images. Using Tensorflow, we relied on a pretrained deep learning model to detect objects on the video received from the UAV. For this experiment we used the SSD multi-box detector [26] trained on the ImageNet dataset [27].

Upon detecting an object, the module sends the detected-object frames to the ground control station of the SWIFTERS platform using ROS messages. The platform then sends the detected frames to the database and to the User Interface which displays them on the map (as a pin) using the current location of the UAV. This allows the user of the SWIFTERS platform to receive alerts of the objects detected, their location and view the image with the detected object. The Live Feed and Detection module can be extended to enable other image processing requirements in disaster management operations and accommodate different detection models and algorithms.

The Live Feed and Detection module can either run in the same window with the main user interface of the SWIFTERS platform or run in different/ individual screens from the same or a different computer. The Live Feed and Detection modules can be initiated for any number of UAVs, as long as the

computer can support their resources requirements and it is connected to the same network.

C. Mobile App interface to DJI UAVs

To enable the communication between the UAV and the SWIFTERS platform, an Android app was created. The device running the SWIFTERS app is connected to the remote controller of the UAV while the SWIFTERS app acts as a mediator between the platform and the UAV. The app enables task commands received from the User Interface of the SWIFTERS to be sent to the UAV. At the same time, it allows receiving the telemetry and other important data from the UAV and sending them to the SWIFTERS interface. This dual-communication functionality of the app is achieved by implementing both the ROS library [20] and the Rosbridge API [28]. This gives the ability to pass messages from the SWIFTERS platform to the Android app as JSON objects which can then be passed through an event bus to the SDK library for the UAV unit at hand (in our case the DJI mobile SDK for Android devices). The specified SDK will handle the correct execution of the command that was sent to the app. A simple diagram of the inner workings of the Android app is shown in Fig. 5. The application starts with a ROS connection handling class which connects to the SWIFTERS platform using the Rosbridge API, and at the same time passes any ROS message received to the event bus. Once the connection is established, the main activity of the app takes over the user interface. This activity, shown in Fig. 4, provides real-time video feed from the UAV's camera and displays important information about the current state of the UAV such as the battery of the UAV, its current GPS position and altitude, as well as the battery of the UAV controller.

IV. PERFORMANCE EVALUATION

A. Methodology

To illustrate the functionality and investigate the performance of the proposed SWIFTERS platform a real-life experiment was conducted using the following setup. The SWIFTERS platform was set to run on a laptop pc and a series of events were executed. Firstly, one UAV was attached and tasked to monitor an area for two minutes. As soon as the first task was completed, a second UAV was introduced to the platform and both were tasked to collaboratively monitor an area for two minutes. This process was repeated with three and four UAVs, which instructed to collaboratively monitor the same area for two additional minutes. The time of area monitoring was restricted to two minutes due to the UAV's battery constraints and to avoid interrupting the experiment to change the UAVs batteries.

The experiment lasted for 16 minutes. The Random Access Memory (RAM) consumption as well as the Central Processing Unit (CPU) utilisation of the SWIFTERS application were recorded before and throughout the usage of the platform.

B. Equipment

For the experiment, we used two DJI Mavic UAVs and two DJI Spark UAVs. The DJI Mavic UAVs are equipped

Fig. 2. The User Interface of the SWIFTERS platform

Fig. 3. The user interface of the Live UAV Video Streaming and Detection module

with a 4K camera stabilised by a 3-axis mechanical gimbal. They offer 27 minutes of flight time at a maximum altitude of 500m (regulated) in an area of 7Km distance. The DJI Spark UAVs weight 400g and are equipped with a 12 MP camera. They offer a flight time of 15 minutes, operating at a maximum altitude of 30m and have a maximum transition distance of 2Km. All UAVs used are equipped with a GPS satellite positioning system.

The SWIFTERS ground control and user interface was used on an Intel Core i7-7820HQ processor computer with an octa-

Fig. 4. The user interface of the Mobile Interface App.

core 2.90GHZ CPU, 16GB RAM and a Intel Kaby Lake GT2 graphics card. On the Computer we use the 64-bit Ubuntu 18.04.02 LTS. The SWIFTERS mobile app was installed on four Android phones with 1.6GHz octa-core processor, 3GB RAM and 16GB of storage.

V. RESULTS

A. Ground Control Application

As discussed, to evaluate the reliability and scalability of the SWIFTERS software application, we undertook an experiment with 4 UAVs while logging the RAM and CPU requirements of the application. The results are demonstrated in Fig. 6.

As shown, when we started the software, the RAM requirement reached 443 MB while the CPU requirements were on 15% of the total processing power of the unit. When we

Fig. 5. Class diagram of the Mobile Application

Fig. 6. RAM and CPU consumed during the evaluation of the SWIFTERS Ground Control application

loaded the maps, the RAM requirement and CPU requirements elevated to 892.3 Mb of RAM and 27% CPU. This was expected, since to visualise maps it is required to load the maps tile-sets (images) to RAM. We can observe that RAM maintained the same level throughout the running of the application while the CPU level dropped after loading the maps. When we connected the UAVs, one by one on the platform, we observed small peaks and drops on the CPU requirements ranging from 13% to 12% processing power.

Overall, we can observe that while loading the maps is a computationally expensive task, the addition of more UAVs on the platform does not affect dramatically the resources requirements of the platform. This suggests the potential of connecting even more UAVs without compromising the running of the platform. This results indicate the scalability of the SWIFTERS platform and the robust operation of multiple UAVs on a single machine.

B. Live Feed and Detection Module

Detecting people and vehicles, as well as undertaking other image processing tasks enables utilising fully the advantages UAVs have to offer. However, while this is a very important feature for disaster assessments, it can strain the memory and processing resources. A seven minutes experiment was undertaken to evaluate the performance of the Live Feed and Detection module in terms of CPU and RAM consumption. The experiment evaluated the performance of the module with and without activating the detection module. To achieve that, we first enabled the module, and then enabled and disabled the detection module in two repetitions. We logged the CPU and RAM consumption throughout the usage of the module. Fig. 7 demonstrates the results.

Fig. 7. RAM and CPU consumed during the evaluation of the Live Feed and Detection Module

The Live Feed and Detection module required 932 MB and around 12% of the processing power when initiated (see Fig. 7). When the detection module is enabled we can observe the RAM requirements elevating to almost 2GB and remaining there throughout the usage of the Live Streaming and Detection module. This was expected since this is the memory that the object detection module used requires. If we would like to minimise the requirements, smaller models shall be used that do not occupy that much of the available RAM.

Furthermore, we can observe that the CPU peaks at around 35% of the processing power when the detection is enabled and drops to 12% when the detection is disabled in a consistent manner. This demonstrates the processing power required to process the image frames and detect the objects. If we would like to minimise the processing requirements we could minimise the frames per second that are being processed or minimise the size of the images that are processed. Additionally, improvements in terms of minimising the size of the model used for the detection will have an important impact on the CPU requirements as well.

C. Mobile Interface App

During the experiment we also logged the performance requirements of the SWIFTERS mobile app which enables the communication between the UAVs with the SWIFTERS platform. The application consumes on average 150MBs of RAM and it can go up to 297MB of RAM. In terms of CPU, the application demanded 35% of the available processing

power of the mobile device. The results provide evidence of the good performance of the application but also suggest avoiding the usage of any resource expensive applications in parallel to guaranty the stable performance of the application.

VI. CONCLUSION AND OUTLOOK

This paper presented SWIFTERS, a multi-drone platform for disaster management. SWIFTERS enables the utilisation of multiple drones throughout the lifecycle of disaster management from monitoring disaster outbreaks, to carrying out situational assessment and mapping affected areas after the disaster. Although multiple UAV platforms exist, they are limited in terms of enabling multi-UAV operations - such as multiple UAV collaboratively searching.

SWIFTERS aims to fill this gap and offer a user friendly environment for controlling multiple UAVs. It allows sending commands to individual UAVs or instructing UAVs to collaboratively undertake a searching task. In addition, it enables the receiving of real-time video feed from the UAVs and uses image processing algorithms for detecting people and objects of interest.

Future work will look into improving the usability of the platform while extensive experiments on the scalability of all the components used will be undertaken. Object avoidance algorithms and multi-sensor generated maps will be integrated. Moreover, this platform shall be enhanced with further features explicitly designed to assist disaster management and emergency response.

Videos from real-life testings and demonstrations of the platform are available at <https://www.kios.ucy.ac.cy/swifters/>

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